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DATA ANALYSIS METHODS FOR LOW-COST AIR QUALITY SENSORS

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Abstract: Low-cost air quality sensors have the potential to contribute substantially to modelling of air quality in the form of generation of new knowledge, model validation and model input. Unfortunately, the poor or unknown data quality delivered by many low-cost air quality sensors hampers their widespread use in modelling and other areas. To contribute to the creation of this consensus, applied two outlier detection methodologies and five gap filling methodologies to a case study. We showed that erroneous data can be detected in a fully automated way, and that point and contextual outlier detection methodologies can be applied to low-cost air pollution data and yield meaningful results. The linear interpolation showed the best performance for gap filling for low-cost air pollution sensors. In conclusion, data cleaning procedures are important, and the presented methods can form part of a generalised data processing methodology for low-cost air pollution sensors.

Key words: *Air Pollution; Quality control; Missing data; Imputing; AQMesh*

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution models and air pollution measurements are intimately connected in that measurements are used for calibration, validation and as model input, and models are used for spatial and temporal interpolation and extrapolation of measurements. Previously, financial constraints have meant that only a low number of air quality stations were available, which thus hampered the interplay between models and measurements. A new generation of low-cost sensors promises to alleviate this problem by allowing an increase in the number of stations without an increase in the budget (Kumar et al. 2015). Unfortunately, many low-cost air quality sensors suffer from poor or unknown data quality, thus hindering more widespread adoption (Snyder et al. 2013, Rai et al. 2017). A contributing factor to this problem is the lack of a consensus on data processing methodologies for low-cost air pollution sensors, since most previous studies on sensor performance have used the data directly from the sensor without further data processing. To contribute to the creation of this consensus, we propose that a generic data processing methodology could be broken down into the steps illustrated in Figure 1, based on the framework presented by van Zoest et al. (2018). To limit the scope of the present study, focus is only on quality control and outlier detection as well as gap filling. The present study is an expanded version of the study by Ottosen and Kumar (2019).

Figure 1. Steps in the proposed generic data processing methodology for low-cost air quality sensors. The steps marked with green are the focus of the present study.

MEASUREMENTS

The measurements used for the development of the data processing methodology consist of a time series measurement from 10 July 2017 to 26 June 2018 with a single AQMesh sensor (Environmental Instruments Ltd, UK; www.aqmesh.com). The sensor consists of five electrochemical low-cost sensors that measured the species NO, NO₂, SO₂, CO and O₃ at 15 minutes temporal resolution. The sensor pod also measured temperature, relative humidity and atmospheric pressure. A proprietary algorithm is applied to the measurements to correct for the influence of temperature, relative humidity and cross-interference of the different species.

The sensor pod was mounted on the stand of a bus stop in the University of Surrey (Guildford, Surrey, UK), campus area, to increase the understanding of air pollution exposure at bus stops. The sensor was mounted at 2.7 m above ground level. The bus stop was being serviced six times per hour in daytime for the stand immediately next to the sensor, and twelve times per hour for the stand a bit further away.

DATA PROCESSING METHODOLOGY

Erroneous data can have many different data patterns caused by different processes such as sensor errors, data logger errors, network connectivity errors or simply exceptional situations in terms of air pollution. In the present study, two kinds of erroneous data are removed from the measurement data. These are termed *errors* and *outliers* to distinguish them from each other. Errors are groups of data with extreme values or extreme statistical properties compared to the rest of the dataset. These are removed in the process termed *Quality Control (QC)*. Contrary to this, outliers are characterised as single data points that are significantly dissimilar to their neighbouring points. These are removed in the process termed *Outlier Detection*. Lastly, different gap filling methodologies are compared using cross-validation.

Quality Control (QC)

The AQMesh sensor comes with a status tag for each species, which was used as a first step of quality control. The status can take on six values being *stabilizing*, *rebasng*, *greater than upper limit*, *less than lower limit*, *valid* and *N/A*. No values are recorded while the status tag is *stabilizing*. Only measurements with the *valid* status were retained.

A visual inspection of the data showed that some of the sensors reported erroneous measurements despite having a *valid* status. The erroneous measurements are seen as abrupt changes in the mean and/or the variance of the time series and have to be removed as part of the quality control. To detect these points, the Pruned Exact Linear Time (PELT) algorithm (Killick et al. 2012) was used. The measurements classified as erroneous was assigned their own status tag called *error*.

Outlier Detection

Many outlier detection methodologies, aimed at many different types of outliers, have been presented in the literature (Chandola et al. 2009). To limit the scope of the present study, two commonly applied outlier detection methods were selected for comparison:

- *k*-Nearest Neighbour (*k*-NN) is one of the simplest outlier detection methodologies and serves as an example of a point outlier detection method. This method utilizes the fact that data are multivariate.

- Regression-based outlier detection is an example of a contextual outlier detection method. This approach has the advantage to take the temporal aspect of the data into account. In the present study, the AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model, which is one of the commonly applied methods, is used.

For details about the implementation of the two outlier detection methods, see Ottosen and Kumar (2019).

Gap Filling

To validate the performance of the different gap-filling methods, cross-validation was applied following similar approaches such as presented by Junninen et al. (2004). To be able to discern between the performance of the different gap-filling methods, a validation dataset consisting of combinations of gap length (0–100 data points), gap proportion (5–50% of time series) and gap location with large impacts on the resulting distributions were designed. For details, see Ottosen and Kumar (2019).

Many gap filling methods have been presented in the literature. To limit the scope of the present study, three univariate and two multivariate gap filling methods were selected for implementation:

- Univariate linear interpolation. This method is selected in the present study as one of the simplest gap filling methods. In Junninen et al. (2004) this method performed best among the univariate methods.
- Cubic spline fitting. This method is included as an example of a slightly more complicated method, including more data points on each side of the gap.
- Univariate neural networks. The most complicated gap filling method is Neural Networks (NN). In this case, a feedforward neural networks with a single hidden layer and lagged inputs is implemented in the `nnetar` function in the forecast package in R.
- Multivariate linear regression. For multivariate gap filling, multivariate linear regression was selected, as this is one of the simplest multivariate approaches. This was implemented such that the missing species was fitted as a linear function of the remaining four species.
- Multivariate neural networks. As an example of a more complicated multivariate approach, the `nnetar` function from the forecast package in R was used again, but this time with the remaining species as input.

RESULTS

Quality Control

A summary of the percentage of data classified as the different status for the different species is shown in Table 1. As can be seen, especially the *less than lower limit*, but also the *error* status tag is influencing many data points. The *error* status tag is especially pronounced for SO₂, whereas *less than lower limit* particularly influences NO and CO. In total, more than 10 % of the data are lost by this procedure, which will have a substantial influence on any subsequent analyses.

Table 1. Percentage of each quality tag for each species from the AQMesh sensor. The average is the average percentage of low-quality data across species for the specific quality tag. The total column represents an error in one of the species for row 2-7 and a valid data point for all five species for row 8. The table is adapted from Ottosen and Kumar (2019).

	NO	NO ₂	SO ₂	CO	O ₃	Average	Total
1 Data before quality control	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
2 Missing data	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
3 Stabilizing	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
4 Rebasing	1.1	1.1	1.1	0.6	1.1	1.0	1.1
5 Less Than Lower Limit	11.7	0.0	3.4	14.3	3.4	6.6	22.1
6 Greater than Upper Limit	0.0	3.9	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.9	3.9
7 Error	0.7	0.0	12.8	0.0	0.0	2.7	13.6
8 Data after quality control	85.3	93.8	81.5	84.0	93.8	87.7	62.7

Outlier Detection

Figure 2. Histograms of the data classified as normal data and outliers by the k-NN and ARIMA outlier detection methods. The species are NO₂ and O₃ chosen since the difference between the two methods is particularly striking for these species.

Histograms for the data classified as respectively *Normal data* and *Outliers* are shown in Figure 2. It is evident from Figure 2 that the two outlier detection methods are classifying different sets of data as outliers. Whereas the *k*-NN algorithm clearly detects data with a different distribution compared to the normal data (respectively higher for NO₂ and lower for O₃), the ARIMA method classifies data with a similar distribution as the normal data. As shown in Ottosen and Kumar (2019), the ARIMA method also detects significantly more outliers compared to the *k*-NN method, although there is a large overlap between the two.

Gap Filling

Figure 3. Correlation coefficient between the original data and the filled data for the three univariate gap filling methods as a function of gap length (*h*). Black (linear interpolation), orange (univariate neural networks), blue (spline interpolation). Figure from Ottosen and Kumar (2019).

An example of the results of the gap filling methods is shown in Figure 3. It is evident that the linear interpolation have the best performance of the three univariate methods, and that the performance of all three methods decrease as a function of gap length, more so for the spline method compared to the others. Similar results are found for the multivariate case, and the reader is referred to Ottosen and Kumar (2019) for further details.

CONCLUSION

This study is a first step towards a consensus on data processing methodologies for low-cost air pollution sensors in a number of ways. We have shown how the PELT algorithm could be used to remove erroneous data. The AQMesh dataset used here contained a substantial number of outliers, but differences from species to species were large. Two outlier detection methodologies were applied to a low-cost air pollution sensor data set and their strengths and weaknesses were discussed. k -NN retains more data if all five species have to be included in the analysis, whereas ARIMA retains more data on a species by species level. Three univariate and two multivariate gap filling techniques were applied. Linear interpolation showed the best performance. The performance of the different gap-filling methodologies was found to depend strongly on gap length and gap percentage.

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